

Motivation to shape the future of education with Artificial Intelligence: An international comparison between Switzerland and China

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ABSTRACT

As digital technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) continue to reshape educational environments, understanding the motivations of student teachers is critical to developing effective teacher education programmes. This study cross-culturally validates the (D) FIT-Choice (Digital Factors Influencing Teaching Choice) scale and examines motivational differences among 416 student teachers in Switzerland and China. The results offer partial validation of the (D)FIT-Choice scale, with several higher-order factors demonstrating acceptable to strong internal consistency, but limitations in model fit for some factors, indicating the need for further refinement to ensure cross-cultural applicability. When comparing the motivations of Swiss and Chinese student teachers, Swiss student teachers reported stronger social utility values and intrinsic motivations than their Chinese counterparts, suggesting a focus on personal fulfilment, social contribution and aligning career choice with personal identity, possibly shaped by Switzerland's individualistic culture and civic engagement. In contrast, Chinese student teachers showed higher perceived digital teaching competence and greater enthusiasm for integrating AI into education, differences that may reflect national educational strategies and technological infrastructures, such as China's long-standing investment in educational digitalisation and the presence of AI-focused education initiatives. These results reveal different levels of willingness to shape the future of education with AI, highlighting how cultural and systemic factors influence the motivation of student teachers. In general, this study highlights how sociocultural, economic and technological contexts shape the motivations of future teachers, emphasising the importance of adapting teacher education to local contexts to prepare future teachers to actively participate in the digital transformation of education.

1. Introduction

Throughout the world, digital technologies and recent advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) are reshaping the landscape of education. Students from primary to secondary education are using computers in a daily basis, the internet offers many resources for learning, and AI applications are providing human-like conversations with increased adaptability and interactivity useful for personalized learning experiences. These technological changes also bring about significant changes in the content to be learned by students at different educational levels. Programming, for example, has become a core subject in the curricula of many countries where the teaching of programming is compulsory from an early age. Beyond programming, media literacy and AI literacy are becoming crucial skills for today's world. From the teachers' point of

view, digital media become tools that can be useful to achieve the pedagogical objectives they set. Incorporating digital media in their teaching practices can help students achieve their learning goals and develop the required skills to use these tools in the present and future. Also, specific applications of AI reveal the potential that these technologies have, with AI being able to take on different roles that call into question the role of the teacher. For instance, AI can take on the role of providing adaptive teaching strategies, automatic and predictive assessment, and educational decision-making [1].

This scenario posed by digital media and AI has led the academic community to reflect on the role of teachers. As a result of this reflection process, for example, different theoretical frameworks have been created specifying the knowledge and competences that teachers should acquire. Examples include the European Digital Competence Framework

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for Educators [2], the AI Competency Framework by Teachers [3], the five dimensions of Chinese teachers' digital literacy [62] or academic work defining AI Literacy for teachers (i.e.; [63,64]). For instance, on the one hand, UNESCO's (2024) AI Competency Framework for Teachers defines 15 competencies across five dimensions - human-centred mindset, ethics of AI, AI foundations and applications, AI pedagogy, and AI for professional development - categorized into three progression levels: acquire, deepen, and create. It aims to fill the gap in teacher training for the AI era by guiding national frameworks, informing training programs, and supporting teachers' ethical AI integration and professional growth. On the other hand, the Chinese Teachers' Digital Literacy Framework defines five key dimensions: digital awareness, technical knowledge and skills, application, social responsibility, and professional development. It highlights the importance of equipping teachers with the ability to leverage digital technologies for problem-solving, innovation, and optimizing teaching practices. This comprehensive framework offers a clear structure for training and evaluating teachers' digital literacy, encompassing 5 first-level, 13 second-level, and 33 third-level dimensions [62].

However, while it is essential that teacher education programmes equip future educators with these competences, an equally important dimension is to understand the motivations that drive people to become teachers in the first place. These motivations can profoundly influence the ease with which new teachers adopt and integrate digital and AI-based pedagogical strategies. Understanding these career choice motivations offers valuable insights into how teacher education programmes can foster not only the necessary technical skills, but also the mindset and willingness to adapt to the demands of modern education. Furthermore, understanding possible cultural differences is also key to adapt different programs to the cultural situations and needs.

Therefore, unlike other studies that focus on general motivation theories such as expectancy-value theory [12] or self-determination theory [46], the current study focuses on career choice motivation. Concretely, it explores and compares student teacher motivations to become a teacher in times of digital change in two regions: Switzerland and China. The "Digital Factors Influencing Teacher Choice" or (D) FIT-Choice model [14,15] is especially suited to studying AI-related teaching motivation since it allows for a nuanced assessment of how future teachers weigh technological transformations against traditional values like social utility and intrinsic career appeal. This focus contributes to the originality of the study by providing the first cross-cultural validation of the (D)FIT-Choice scale in diverse contexts like Switzerland and China, revealing how cultural, systemic, and technological factors uniquely shape motivations amid AI-driven educational shifts, and offering insights for tailoring teacher education programs to foster digital readiness. Overall, this comparison can help us understand the factors affecting the motivation to become future teachers in societies being shaped by digital technologies.

In brief, this study makes three main contributions. First, it provides cross-cultural testing of the (D)FITChoice scale, which includes new items related to AI, and identifies which dimensions show sufficient reliability and invariance for use in different contexts. Second, it offers a comparative analysis of the motivations of Swiss and Chinese student teachers, with a focus on digitalisation and AI, thus illustrating how cultural conditions determine the willingness to consider in the digital transformation of education. Thirdly, it derives implications for the design of teacher training programmes that aim to foster both traditional values of social utility and preparation related to digital technology and AI, in a way that is sensitive to contextual conditions.

2. State of the art

2.1. Motives for becoming a teacher in a digital era

Existing research on motives for becoming a teacher highlights the importance of understanding student teachers' motivations to address

teacher's satisfaction with the profession, as well as associated problems such as teacher shortages and low retention [4,5]. For instance, some studies have identified three main categories of motives: altruistic, intrinsic and extrinsic [6,7]. While altruistic motives, such as making a difference and contributing to students' development, are associated with higher academic engagement and lower dropout rates [8], a combination of high intrinsic and low extrinsic motives has been associated with better performance [9], being at the same time high extrinsic motives associated with stress-inducing thoughts [10].

A widely used model that specifies different factors that are considered when deciding to become a teacher is the Factors Influencing Teacher Choice (FIT-Choice) Model [11]. This model is based on the Expectancy Value Theory [12], which explains people's motivation to take a specific action based on their perceived expectancy of achieving that action, the value and costs associated to the defined goal. Therefore, the FIT-Choice model explains that the choice of the teaching career is made based on perceived abilities to become a teacher, the value assigned to the teaching profession (intrinsic value, personal utility value, and social utility value) and the associated costs and return of being a teacher, and influenced at the same time by prior experiences teaching and learning [11].

However, given the digital changes happening in education, it is important to understand whether student teachers are considering this situation when deciding to become a teacher, especially if these changes are expected to change their role as a teacher as well as the content they will be required to teach [13]. In this context, the (D)FIT-Choice scale [14,15] assesses the reasons that student teachers have for becoming a teacher in times of digital change (see Fig. 1). Following the order of the model, it begins considering socialization influences that may have shaped the decision to become a teacher, including prior experiences as a student as well as using digital technologies for education. Then, the self-perceived ability as a teacher also with technologies is also assessed, as well as the level to which students consider that teaching requires a high task demand as well as task return. The idea of whether teaching was chosen as a second option is also considered in fallback career. Then, different types of values associated with the teaching profession are assessed, including intrinsic value of the teaching career, utilitarian aspects related to one's own benefits, and value that the person brings to society. Finally, the satisfaction with the career choice is considered.

Based on the (D)FIT-Choice model, studies done in Switzerland indicate that student teachers are not precisely considering the digital changes happening in education, with motives such as contributing to the digital society, or using digital means to teach among the least important aspects [14,15]. Furthermore, the consideration of digital-related aspects correlates with personal utility value motivations such as job security, rather than with bringing value to society. These findings are significant because they highlight a potential gap between the priorities of teacher education and the motivations of student teachers. If future teachers do not consider the impact of digitalization, they may be less prepared to adapt to technological changes, limiting their ability to foster a digitally literate generation.

2.2. Comparative studies on motives for becoming a teacher

Comparative studies on motives to become a teacher offer a broader perspective by examining the reasons why people from diverse cultural and economic backgrounds decide to pursue a teaching career. They provide "wonderful 'natural experiments' to contrast the impact of salient cultural features" ([16], p. 186). These studies highlight both universal motivations and the ways in which local factors, such as social expectations and educational policies, influence the attractiveness of the teaching profession. By analysing different regions, it is possible to identify which motivational factors transcend national borders and which are determined by specific cultural or structural conditions. This international perspective enriches the understanding of the reasons why people choose to become teachers and provides a basis for specific

Fig. 1. (D)FIT-Choice model adapted from Martínez-Moreno & Petko [15].

teacher recruitment and retention strategies that consider the different needs and values of each context.

In a study comparing Australia, United States, Germany and Norway where the FIT-Choice scale was used, it was seen that motives were very similar across samples, being the highest rated motivations intrinsic value, perceived teaching ability, the desire to make a social contribution, work with children and adolescents and having positive prior experiences in education [17]. In another study, Swiss and German student teachers were also found to be highly intrinsically motivated and wanting to work with children and adolescents, specially when comparing it to Ukrainian student teachers [10]. However, while these studies focused on European countries, when comparing countries from even more different contexts, bigger differences appear. In a study where Canadian and Omani student teachers were compared, it was seen that while Canadian student teachers expressed higher levels of individual motivations and social utility value, Omani student teachers indicated more socio-cultural influences and higher levels of fallback career [18]. In a special issue, Turkey, the United States, People’s Republic of China, the Netherlands, Croatia, Germany and Switzerland were compared [16], and something that they found is that US student teachers reported higher motivations from social utility values, teaching abilities, intrinsic value, and prior teaching and learning experiences than Chinese student teachers, who reported higher levels of fallback career. Finally, in a review of international evidence it was seen that teachers in Shanghai, Taiwan, South Korea and Singapore were the most likely to consider that teaching fits in with personal responsibilities such as family life, especially when comparing it to teachers in England [19].

In the case of China, existing research highlights socio-cultural factors as key external influences on teachers’ motivation [20,21]. In the study by Ye et al. [21], China’s paternalistic traditions and socialist stratification policies encouraged individuals to pursue teaching, while social influences including parental expectations, diminished motivation and led some participants to consider leaving the profession.

Chinese student teachers also ranked personal utility value as a decisive factor for becoming a teacher [20]. Chinese society also enhances the status of teaching through financial support recognizing it as an esteemed in-system profession to attract and retain talent, with salary playing a significant role in student teacher’s motives specially when comparing to other countries such as Australia and New Zealand [20, 22]. Meanwhile, Swiss student teachers have been seen to be highly motivated by intrinsic motivations, followed by a willingness to shape the future of children and adolescents, without being influenced by their social background but rather by prior positive experiences in education [14,15].

2.3. Digital education landscapes in Switzerland and China

Given that the current study is focused on Switzerland and China, it is important to explore both contexts, especially their educational and digital educational landscape. These factors can at the same time be critical to understanding possible differences in the motives to become a teacher that guide student teachers in both countries.

First, from a general cultural perspective, it can be helpful to refer to Hofstede’s cultural dimensions. These dimensions, which provide a framework for understanding cultural differences across nations and their influence on behaviour and societal norms [23,24]. These dimensions have received several critiques such as a generalization within countries without differentiating between regional, ethnic or individual differences [25], it may still be a good starting point to understand countries in general terms. For instance, Power Distance refers to the degree to which less powerful members of a society accept and expect an unequal distribution of power, while Individualism contrasts cultures that prioritise personal goals and autonomy over those that are more Collectivistic empathising group cohesion and loyalty. Based on this, when comparing Switzerland and China based on Hofstede’s cultural dimensions, relevant differences appear. First, Switzerland scores low on

power distance and high on individualism, indicating a society that values equal distribution of power and individual actions. In contrast, China's high-power distance and low individualism score reflect a more hierarchical and collectivist society. These cultural differences can influence the educational approaches in each country, with the Swiss system emphasizing individual development and the Chinese system focusing more on collective achievement and respect for authority. At the same time, this may influence the perceived role of the teacher, adopting a more authoritarian perspective and being more valued at a societal level in the case of China [24].

An index in the context of this study, given its focus on digitalization of education, is the innovation index of both countries. In terms of innovation, Switzerland has consistently led the world, ranking as the most innovative economy for 14 consecutive years as of 2024, with a Global Innovation Index score of 67.5. At the same time, China, while not in the top 10, has made significant strides in innovation, ranking 11th globally in 2024 and being the only middle-income economy in the top 30, with a score of 56.3, and Hong Kong ranking 18th with a score of 50.1 (World Intellectual Property Organization., [26]). Meanwhile, the IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking sets Switzerland in second place with a score of 93.15 and Hong Kong in the 7th place with a score of 88.11, while China has a score of 82.59 [27]. In formal education, when looking at the time that students spend at schools on digital devices for learning as well as for leisure, while Switzerland is around two and a half hours a day, Hong Kong students spend around three hours a day [28].

In the context of education, Switzerland follows a federal system characterized by a high level of decentralization that allows for some differences between regions or cantons. Compulsory education lasts 11 years, starting with two years of kindergarten at age four in the case of Zurich, followed by six years of primary school and three years of lower secondary school. After compulsory education, students can choose between vocational education or upper secondary schools, which prepare them for higher education. In terms of education curriculum, each region or canton can follow a slightly different educational program. In the case of Zurich, it adopted the Lehrplan 21 which intends to integrate digital skills throughout compulsory education [61]. Concretely, the Curriculum 21 makes media and computer science a transversal subject, meaning that all compulsory education teachers need to be knowledgeable about these disciplines and be able to introduce them in their daily practice. However, in terms of Artificial Intelligence, it does not have any specific curriculum yet.

In contrast, China follows a more centralized structure with some differences between mainland China, including Shenzhen, and Hong Kong due to the "one country, two systems" policy applied in the latter. In mainland China, including Shenzhen, the system is highly competitive and exam-oriented, with a strong emphasis on academic achievement. The structure typically includes six years of primary education, three years of junior secondary education, and three years of senior secondary education. On the other hand, Hong Kong's system has similarities to mainland China but maintains some distinct aspects given the influence of its British colonial past. In this case, it offers a more diverse curriculum and places a greater emphasis on English language education compared to mainland China. China, particularly in urban areas like Shenzhen, has seen a rapid growth in digital education. The country has embraced online learning platforms and digital resources on a massive scale, especially in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, China launched a "National Online Cloud Classroom" for students from grades 1 to 12, effectively moving 200 million children to online learning. China's AI education, especially in K12, is at the forefront. For example, Hong Kong Education Bureau has released the regular computational thinking and AI curricula for all primary and secondary school students from July 2023. In Feb 2024, Ministry of Education issued a guidance on enhancing AI literacy in primary and secondary schools, indicating that younger primary school children should focus on exploring and experiencing AI technology, while older primary school

children and middle school students should concentrate on understanding and applying AI concepts, and high school students should engage in project creation and advanced applications [29]. The government advocates for the growth of an AI-proficient teaching workforce by enhancing teacher training and recruiting experts from universities, research institutions, and high-tech companies to serve as part-time educators. It prioritizes awareness raising in the early primary years, comprehension and application in upper primary and middle school, and project development along with advanced applications in high school. Additionally, schools are encouraged to incorporate AI education into after-school programs and research activities, promoting collaboration among industry, academia, research, and practical applications [29].

While both systems recognize the importance of digital education, China's approach is more oriented towards adopting initiatives fostering AI literacy, and fast in implementing them, while this is not something considered in Switzerland yet.

3. Current study

Given that the motivations to become a teacher have been found to vary in different countries, the current study aims to investigate whether this is also the case for digital-related motives. Although it has been seen that Swiss student teachers rarely consider digital-related aspects when deciding to become a teacher, and if they do so for personal utilitarian reasons, it is important to understand whether this can be generalized to other contexts, such as China. China's leadership in technology may influence how digital transformation in education is valued. Comparing contexts can help tailor teacher education programs and support a global dialogue on preparing teachers for a digitally driven future.

Digital technologies have entered the classroom differently in Switzerland than in China, possibly being also the case that the considerations of digital technologies also vary. Based on this assumption, the main objective of the current study is to explore the motivations that student teachers in Hong Kong and Shenzhen have for becoming a teacher and see to what extent these motivations are different in comparison to the motivations of student teachers in Zurich. Concretely, the study aims to use the (D)FIT-Choice scale to collect data on the reasons to become a teacher as well as to test its validity and reliability with a mixed sample of Swiss and Chinese student teachers. Then, based on the data collected from both samples of student teachers this study aims to explore whether there are significant differences that could be explained based on contextual differences. Summarizing, the study pursues the following objectives:

- (1) To examine the reliability and factorial structure of the (D)FIT-Choice scale in Swiss and Chinese samples.
- (2) To test the cross-cultural applicability of the higher-order factors of the (D)FIT-Choice model through measurement invariance analyses.
- (3) To compare Swiss and Chinese student teachers' motivations, with particular attention to digital- and AI-related motives, while considering the limitations imposed by measurement invariance.

These objectives are reflected in the following research questions:

- RQ1. Is the (D)FIT-Choice scale a valid and reliable instrument across different cultural contexts?
- RQ2. Are there differences between Chinese and Swiss student teachers based on the (D)FIT-Choice scale?

4. Methodology

4.1. Sample

Switzerland and China were selected as contrasting cases because

they differ markedly in cultural value orientations (e.g., individualism–collectivism, power distance), in the structure and governance of their education systems, and in the pace and policy emphasis of educational digitalisation and AI integration. These contrasts provide a theoretically meaningful context in which to test the cross-cultural applicability of the (D)FIT-Choice scale (RQ1) and to explore how socio-cultural and technological conditions shape both traditional and AI-related motives to become a teacher (RQ2).

The sample of this study consists of 416 student teachers, 44 % from Switzerland ($N = 183$), and 56 % from China ($N = 233$). The response rate was 65 % in Switzerland and 71 % in China. Only complete questionnaires were accepted, so there were no incomplete or invalid responses to be excluded. Data were collected between 2023 and 2024 at two institutions in each country, Switzerland (CH) and China (CN). Participants were contacted via their institutional email accounts and participation was entirely voluntary and uncompensated, no incentives were offered. While this approach minimizes coercion, it may introduce self-selection bias, potentially overrepresenting students with higher overall motivation or greater interest in the study topic. Prior to analysis, records with missing or incomplete responses were excluded, yielding the final sample of 416. The table below shows the number of participants from each country and the demographic specifications.

4.2. Instrument

For the present study, the (D)FIT-Choice scale including items related to AI in Education was used [15]. This scale assesses the reasons that student teachers have for engaging in teaching. Since the original version of the (D)FIT-Choice scale was developed and validated in German, it was translated to English to collect data from this sample. The forward translation was performed by a bilingual researcher familiar with the FIT-Choice terminology, after which domain experts in teacher education in China conducted an expert review to evaluate semantic, idiomatic, experiential, and conceptual equivalence and to identify culture-specific ambiguities. Revisions were resolved by consensus among the translators and investigators. A formal back-translation was not undertaken; instead, we relied on iterative expert validation to ensure content equivalence and readability. The final English version was then administered to the sample of Chinese student teachers. These steps ensured that the English version of the questionnaire was suitable for comparison with the German version, thus allowing meaningful conclusions to be drawn from both the Chinese and Swiss samples.

4.3. Research design

Data collection followed a different procedure in each of the two countries. On the one hand, the data from Switzerland was collected via an online survey hosted in LimeSurvey. On the other hand, since this platform was not accessible to Chinese students due to accessibility restrictions, the survey was hosted in the learning platform used in their studies. In both cases, student teachers had to accept an informed consent indicating that they were aware that their participation was

voluntary and that they could opt-out at any moment, and they also received information about their data being treated anonymously, among other details.

Data analysis was conducted using a combination of jamovi (version 2.3.28) and R (version 4.3.2) to address the research questions regarding the validity, reliability, and cross-cultural differences of the (D)FIT-Choice scale among Swiss and Chinese student teachers. On the one hand, statistical analyses were performed to confirm the validity and reliability of the questionnaire in this new context. The psychometric properties of the tool were tested through reliability analysis and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to validate the questionnaire across both cultural contexts. The 7-point semantic differential items were treated as continuous indicators, consistent with common practice for Likert scales with 5 or more points. Reliability analysis, calculating Cronbach’s alpha (α) and McDonald’s omega (ω) with a threshold of 0.7 for sufficient reliability [30,31], was conducted in jamovi, which facilitated initial data exploration and scale reliability assessment. Additionally, a descriptive analysis was conducted in jamovi to explore the motivations of the participants.

To assess cross-cultural equivalence, configural, metric and scalar invariance testing were performed to evaluate the structure, equivalence of factor loadings and item intercepts across groups. Criteria for metric and scalar invariance will include a difference in CFI < 0.01 ($\Delta\text{CFI} \leq 0.01$) [32]. CFA and measurement invariance models were estimated in R using lavaan (version 0.6–18) using maximum likelihood (ML). The goodness of fit for the CFA was evaluated using the Bentler Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Steiger-Lind Root Mean Square of Approximation (RMSEA), and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), with cut-off criteria set at CFI > 0.90 , TLI > 0.90 , SRMR < 0.08 , and RMSEA < 0.08 [33–37] and a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted.

After validating the questionnaire, comparative analyses were performed between the CH and CN groups using independent sample t -tests in jamovi, leveraging its straightforward interface for group comparisons. Before performing t -tests for independent samples, we inspected the distributions of all scale scores for univariate outliers (box plots and standardised scores) and approximate normality (histograms and Q-Q plots). No serious deviations from normality or extreme outliers were detected. Given the sample sizes in both groups ($n > 180$) and the use of 7-point scales, t -tests are considered robust to minor deviations from normality. Homogeneity of variance was examined using Levene’s test; when this assumption was violated, Welch’s t -test was used instead of Student’s t -test. These t -tests were performed on the observed mean scores of the first-order factors that meet reliability and configural invariance criteria, aiming to explore differences in motivations, particularly the influence of digital-related factors on the decision to pursue a teaching career, with results interpreted cautiously based on the outcomes of the invariance testing. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was adopted. Effect sizes were calculated using Cohen’s d , with thresholds of $d = 0.2$ for small, $d = 0.5$ for medium, and $d = 0.8$ for large effect sizes [38,39].

5. Results

5.1. Reliability analysis and descriptive statistics

The reliability analysis of the (D)FIT-Choice first-order factors (Table 2) revealed generally good internal consistency across both Swiss (CH; $n = 183$) and Chinese (CN; $n = 233$) student teachers, with most factors achieving Cronbach’s alpha (α) and McDonald’s omega (ω) values ≥ 0.80 . For instance, Prior Teaching and Learning Experiences (PTLE: CH $\alpha = 0.887$, CN $\alpha = 0.940$), Perceived Digital Teaching Competence (PDTTC: CH $\alpha = 0.922$, CN $\alpha = 0.934$), and Artificial Intelligence (AI: CH $\alpha = 0.938$, CN $\alpha = 0.966$) demonstrated strong reliability in both groups, as did Satisfaction (SN: CH $\alpha = 0.915$, CN $\alpha = 0.983$).

However, some factors exhibited lower reliability, concretely

Table 1
Sample demographics.

Sample	Age (M, SD)	Experience (M, SD)	Gender (N, %)			
			Women	Men	Other	Not stated
Overall	22.8 (7.88)	0.98 (2.80)	280 (67.3)	133 (32.0)	1 (0.2)	2 (0.5)
Switzerland	28.7 (8.84)	0.90 (4.23)	111 (26.7)	69 (16.6)	1 (0.2)	2 (0.5)
China	18.0 (0.35)	1.04 (0.20)	169 (40.6)	64 (15.4)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Table 2
Reliability statistics (α/ω) of factors (in bold) and items (α/ω if item dropped) in each country.

Code	Items (English translation)	Switzerland (CH)				China (CN)			
		M	SD	α	ω	M	SD	α	ω
	How important are the following reasons for your decision to become a teacher? "I chose to become a teacher because..." 1 (not at all important) - 7 (extremely important)								
PTEL	Prior teaching and learning experiences	5.26	1.43	0.887	0.893	4.86	1.54	0.940	0.941
ptle1	I have had inspirational teachers	5.25	1.65	0.786	0.786	4.90	1.63	0.897	0.898
ptle2	I have had good teachers as role-models	5.19	1.57	0.801	0.802	4.83	1.65	0.900	0.900
ptle3	I have had positive learning experiences	5.35	1.52	0.919	0.919	4.84	1.62	0.938	0.938
PDTU	Prior digital technology use	3.22	1.46	0.862	0.872	4.06	1.68	0.943	0.944
pdtu1	I have had innovative teachers who used technology for education	3.01	1.64	0.723	0.723	3.97	1.79	0.884	0.886
pdtu2	I had teachers who taught me skills to learn effectively with digital media	2.95	1.63	0.790	0.790	3.93	1.83	0.910	0.911
pdtu3	I have had positive learning experiences with educational technologies	3.70	1.68	0.897	0.897	4.29	1.68	0.950	0.950
SI	Social influences	4.01	1.77	0.862	0.870	4.34	1.65	0.884	0.886
si1	My friends think I should become a teacher	4.10	1.95	0.740	0.741	4.44	1.78	0.820	0.823
si2	My family think I should become a teacher	3.63	2.08	0.880	0.880	4.21	1.95	0.858	0.858
si3	People I've worked with think I should become a teacher	4.28	1.96	0.797	0.798	4.38	1.76	0.828	0.830
PTA	Perceived teaching abilities	5.92	0.763	0.761	0.789	5.85	1.04	0.875	0.876
pta1	I have the qualities of a good teacher	6.01	0.868	0.577	0.612	5.92	1.16	0.807	0.808
pta2	I have good teaching skills	5.62	1.127	0.753	0.758	5.72	1.19	0.845	0.845
pta3	Teaching is a career suited to my abilities	6.15	0.745	0.715	0.730	5.91	1.16	0.821	0.821
PDTC	Perceived digital teaching competence	4.19	1.43	0.922	0.923	4.79	1.42	0.934	0.936
pdtc1	I know how to use digital technologies to improve students' learning	4.10	1.58	0.878	0.878	4.71	1.45	0.890	0.893
pdtc2	I know how to use digital technologies to improve teaching	4.24	1.49	0.887	0.888	4.76	1.44	0.928	0.931
pdtc3	I know how to successfully incorporate digital technologies in the classroom	4.22	1.55	0.898	0.899	4.90	1.62	0.892	0.892
FC	Fallback career	2.44	1.38	0.689	0.761	3.22	1.31	0.681	0.747
fc1	I chose the teaching degree programme because I have few chances of working in my desired profession	2.07	1.79	0.538	0.624	3.39	1.94	0.555	0.558
fc2	I chose the teaching degree programme to have an additional career alternative	3.61	2.19	0.732	0.782	3.56	1.62	0.783	0.804
fc3	I would only become a teacher if I couldn't find another job	1.62	1.12	0.553	0.561	2.71	1.44	0.376	0.381
IVT	Intrinsic value teaching	6.48	0.556	0.649	0.652	6.08	0.848	0.836	0.845
ivt1	I am interested in teaching	6.46	0.739	0.530	0.533	6.18	0.947	0.872	0.872
ivt2	I like teaching	6.39	0.761	0.500	0.502	6.03	0.993	0.700	0.700
ivt3	I want to create interesting lessons	6.58	0.674	0.614	0.614	6.02	0.990	0.728	0.728
IVS	Intrinsic value subject	6.11	0.763	0.668	0.720	5.60	1.20	0.910	0.913
ivs1	I find the content of my subjects interesting	6.26	0.837	0.517	0.544	5.65	1.24	0.846	0.849
ivs2	I enjoy dealing with the content of my subjects	6.22	0.838	0.496	0.523	5.69	1.25	0.869	0.872
ivs3	My subjects are important	5.83	1.226	0.748	0.748	5.46	1.40	0.900	0.900
JS	Job security	5.14	1.31	0.879	0.883	5.88	1.16	0.889	0.892
js1	Teaching will offer a steady career path	5.10	1.50	0.857	0.860	5.78	1.30	0.839	0.841
js2	Teaching will provide a reliable income	5.27	1.37	0.854	0.854	6.09	1.22	0.896	0.896
js3	As a teacher you have a secure job	5.06	1.52	0.769	0.771	5.77	1.32	0.781	0.782
TFF	Time for family	4.54	1.63	0.888	0.889	4.31	1.39	0.834	0.852
tff1	Part-time teaching could allow more family time	4.63	1.75	0.861	0.861	4.22	1.64	0.899	0.899
tff2	Teaching hours will fit with the responsibilities of having a family	4.62	1.83	0.804	0.804	4.42	1.61	0.660	0.660
tff3	School holidays will fit with family commitments	4.37	1.83	0.854	0.855	4.29	1.57	0.730	0.730
JT	Job transferability	4.02	1.49	0.769	0.771	4.08	1.31	0.667	0.675
jt1	Teaching is a useful job if you want to be professionally mobile	4.01	1.75	0.699	0.700	3.89	1.60	0.614	0.615
jt2	A teaching qualification is recognized in many parts of the world, and you can work anywhere	4.09	1.84	0.712	0.712	3.77	1.68	0.491	0.493
jt3	A teaching job will allow me to choose where I wish to live	3.95	1.81	0.657	0.657	4.58	1.79	0.604	0.605
SFCA	Shape the future of children and adolescents	5.94	0.952	0.705	0.714	4.81	1.53	0.932	0.932
sfca1	Teaching will allow me to shape child/ adolescent values	6.11	1.12	0.683	0.686	4.88	1.67	0.906	0.907
sfca2	Teaching will allow me to influence the next generation	5.79	1.30	0.512	0.513	4.78	1.56	0.903	0.903
sfca3	As a teacher I can help shape the future of our society	5.91	1.17	0.623	0.627	4.78	1.67	0.895	0.896
ESE	Enhance social equity	5.55	1.25	0.887	0.890	4.73	1.40	0.951	0.952
ese1	Teaching will allow me to raise the ambitions of underprivileged youth	5.89	1.25	0.879	0.879	4.88	1.51	0.947	0.947
ese2	Teaching will allow me to benefit the socially disadvantaged	5.34	1.46	0.794	0.799	4.63	1.44	0.916	0.916
ese3	As a teacher I can help to balance out inequalities in society	5.43	1.43	0.838	0.844	4.67	1.45	0.925	0.925
MSC	Make a social contribution	5.78	1.13	0.821	0.837	4.75	1.56	0.931	0.932
msc1	Teaching allows me to provide a service to society	6.03	1.20	0.699	0.724	4.86	1.70	0.877	0.880
msc2	Teachers make a worthwhile social contribution	6.07	1.13	0.773	0.789	4.81	1.72	0.884	0.886
msc3	Teaching enables me to 'give back' to society	5.25	1.57	0.796	0.797	4.57	1.57	0.933	0.933
WCA	Work with children and adolescents	5.62	1.18	0.904	0.908	4.87	1.28	0.880	0.883
wca1	I want a job that involves working with children/adolescents	5.49	1.36	0.820	0.828	4.77	1.50	0.871	0.872
wca2	I want to work in a child-/adolescent-centred environment	5.31	1.37	0.840	0.848	4.75	1.35	0.822	0.823
wca3	I like working with children/adolescents	6.07	1.13	0.914	0.914	5.08	1.42	0.796	0.799
CDT	Contribute to the digital transformation	4.06	1.42	0.867	0.870	4.13	1.24	0.835	0.850
cdt1	I want to design innovative lessons with digital technologies	4.15	1.62	0.853	0.853	4.25	1.44	0.898	0.899
cdt2	I want to teach young people digital skills	4.02	1.56	0.781	0.781	4.04	1.40	0.697	0.697
cdt3	I want to prepare young people for life in a digital world	4.03	1.60	0.806	0.806	4.11	1.44	0.699	0.699
AI	Artificial Intelligence	4.03	1.61	0.938	0.939	4.28	1.57	0.966	0.966
AI1	I want to use the possibilities offered by artificial intelligence to improve teaching and learning.	4.04	1.79	0.923	0.923	4.27	1.68	0.958	0.958
AI2	I want to prepare students for working with artificial intelligence.	4.35	1.78	0.935	0.936	4.42	1.64	0.963	0.963
AI3	I want to use artificial intelligence to adapt teaching and learning to the digital society.	3.78	1.76	0.917	0.918	4.13	1.69	0.955	0.955
AI4	I want to address the challenges of artificial intelligence in education.	4.09	1.89	0.924	0.925	4.32	1.70	0.959	0.959

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Code	Items (English translation)	Switzerland (CH)				China (CN)			
		M	SD	α	ω	M	SD	α	ω
AI5	I want to contribute to the changes in education brought about by artificial intelligence. For each question below, please rate the extent to which YOU agree it is true about teaching.1 (not at all) - 7 (extremely)	3.90	1.76	0.919	0.920	4.24	1.66	0.956	0.956
EC	Expert career	5.75	0.878	0.746	0.764	5.42	1.13	0.882	0.885
ec1	Do you think teaching requires high levels of expert knowledge?	5.37	1.268	0.590	0.594	5.24	1.26	0.876	0.876
ec2	Do you think teachers need high levels of technical knowledge?	5.73	1.033	0.550	0.573	5.40	1.28	0.779	0.780
ec3	Do you think teachers need a lot of pedagogical and psychological knowledge?	6.15	0.901	0.789	0.799	5.62	1.23	0.837	0.837
HD	High demand	5.88	0.811	0.700	0.720	5.34	1.11	0.885	0.891
hd1	Do you think teachers have a heavy workload?	5.66	1.103	0.512	0.526	5.22	1.20	0.807	0.807
hd2	Do you think teaching is emotionally demanding?	6.14	0.846	0.769	0.769	5.48	1.26	0.914	0.914
hd3	Do you think teaching is hard work?	5.85	1.107	0.456	0.469	5.31	1.23	0.784	0.784
SS	Social status	4.45	1.26	0.890	0.891	5.02	1.18	0.808	0.838
ss1	Do you believe teaching is perceived as a high-status occupation?	4.38	1.39	0.809	0.809	5.53	1.46	0.913	0.913
ss2	Do you believe teaching is a well-respected career?	4.48	1.38	0.856	0.856	4.78	1.34	0.629	0.630
ss3	Do you think teachers feel their occupation has high social status?	4.48	1.40	0.865	0.865	4.76	1.35	0.643	0.644
SY	Salary	5.04	1.08	0.871	0.890	5.56	0.967	0.763	0.839
sy1	Do you think teaching is well paid?	5.14	1.17	0.741	0.744	5.88	1.13	0.498	0.502
sy2	Do you think teachers earn a good salary?	5.20	1.16	0.757	0.760	5.88	1.10	0.515	0.518
sy3	Do you think that teachers benefit from good social benefits (e.g., allowances, pension rights)? For each question below, please rate the extent to which it is true for YOU. 1 (not at all) - 7 (extremely)	4.77	1.31	0.949	0.949	4.91	1.28	0.965	0.966
SD	Social dissuasion	3.26	1.41	0.604	0.641	3.64	1.48	0.822	0.827
sd1	Were you encouraged to pursue careers other than teaching?	3.79	1.94	0.337	0.337	3.88	1.70	0.715	0.715
sd2	Did others tell you teaching was not a good career choice?	2.67	1.84	0.691	0.691	3.38	1.76	0.830	0.830
sd3	Did others influence you to consider careers other than teaching?	3.32	1.89	0.427	0.427	3.65	1.71	0.714	0.715
SN	Satisfaction	6.18	0.902	0.915	0.920	4.93	1.69	0.983	0.984
sn1	How satisfied are you with your choice of becoming a teacher?	6.10	0.992	0.831	0.832	4.87	1.71	0.968	0.968
sn2	How happy are you with your decision to become a teacher?	6.12	0.993	0.840	0.840	4.93	1.71	0.974	0.975
sn3	How determined are you to become a teacher in any case at the end of your studies?	6.31	0.941	0.952	0.952	4.99	1.75	0.984	0.984

Fallback Career in both samples (FC: CH $\alpha = 0.689$, CN $\alpha = 0.681$), Job Transferability in the Chinese sample (JT: CN $\alpha = 0.667$, $\omega = 0.675$), and in the Swiss sample, in Intrinsic Value Teaching (IVT: CH $\alpha = 0.649$, $\omega = 0.652$), Intrinsic Value Subject (IVS: CH $\alpha = 0.668$), and Social Dissuasion (SD: CH $\alpha = 0.604$, $\omega = 0.641$), suggesting potential issues with item consistency or cultural differences in interpretation.

5.2. Confirmatory factor analysis

To assess whether the proposed second-order factor models of the (D)FIT-Choice model held the same structure across Swiss and Chinese student teachers, configural, metric and scalar invariance tests were conducted. Given the complex structure of the (D)FIT-Choice model and

the sample size constraints of this study, it was not feasible to run a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) of the entire model. Instead, single-factor CFAs were conducted to test each higher-order factor separately (see Table 3).

Invariance testing results show that Socialization Influences fails at the configural level (CFI < 0.90, RMSEA > 0.08), indicating that the factor structure is not consistent across groups. CN contributes significantly to misfit across all levels, suggesting cultural differences in how this construct is perceived. Metric and scalar invariance results are not meaningful due to the initial failure. Self-Perception achieves configural invariance (CFI = 0.982), but fails metric (Δ CFI = -0.023) and scalar invariance (Δ CFI = -0.021). The factor structure is consistent across groups, but factor loadings and intercepts differ, likely due to cultural

Table 3

Fit statistics for single-factor CFAs in configural (CI), metric (MI) and scalar (SI) invariance testing of higher-order factors across Swiss and Chinese student teachers.

Higher-order Factor		χ^2	df	p	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA	RMSEA 95 % CI		χ^2 Contribution	
									Lower	Upper	CH	CN
Socialization Influences	CI	1022.173	100	< 0.001	0.884	0.847	0.064	0.199	0.187	0.211	65.03	857.1
	MI	1022.173	111	< 0.001	0.871	0.847	0.108	0.199	0.185	0.213	153.5	868.6
	SI	1155.473	118	< 0.001	0.854	0.836	0.119	0.206	0.192	0.219	275.6	879.9
Self-Perception	CI	49.127	14	< 0.001	0.982	0.961	0.034	0.110	0.077	0.144	14.5	34.6
	MI	98.847	19	< 0.001	0.959	0.935	0.066	0.142	0.109	0.176	52.7	46.2
	SI	143.119	22	< 0.001	0.938	0.938	0.075	0.163	0.132	0.194	82.2	60.9
Task Demand	CI	73.141	14	< 0.001	0.969	0.933	0.058	0.143	0.111	0.176	28.3	44.8
	MI	132.344	19	< 0.001	0.940	0.906	0.093	0.169	0.137	0.202	81.8	50.6
	SI	212.501	22	< 0.001	0.900	0.900	0.107	0.204	0.174	0.234	149.2	63.3
Task Return	CI	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	MI	1729.586	19	< 0.001	0.496	0.204	0.311	0.658	0.627	0.689	189.1	1540.5
	SI	1960.355	22	< 0.001	0.429	0.221	0.419	0.651	0.622	0.680	427.6	1532.7
Intrinsic Value	CI	62.981	14	< 0.001	0.970	0.935	0.066	0.130	0.098	0.163	8.0	54.9
	MI	71.725	19	< 0.001	0.968	0.949	0.076	0.116	0.088	0.145	15.8	55.9
	SI	148.450	22	< 0.001	0.922	0.894	0.103	0.166	0.141	0.192	73.3	75.2
Personal Utility Value	CI	556.099	48	< 0.001	0.779	0.669	0.090	0.226	0.209	0.243	46.652	509.4
	MI	766.730	56	< 0.001	0.691	0.603	0.207	0.247	0.232	0.263	183.1	583.7
	SI	978.418	61	< 0.001	0.601	0.529	0.275	0.269	0.254	0.284	256.2	722.3
Social Utility Value	CI	1030.252	328	< 0.001	0.933	0.923	0.130	0.101	0.094	0.108	373.6	656.6
	MI	1179.618	347	< 0.001	0.921	0.914	0.163	0.107	0.101	0.114	477.1	702.5
	SI	1401.421	360	< 0.001	0.901	0.896	0.168	0.118	0.111	0.124	676.7	724.7

differences. Task Demand achieves marginal configural invariance (CFI = 0.969), but fails metric ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.029$) and scalar invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.040$). The factor structure is mostly consistent across groups, but factor loadings and intercepts differ. Task Return fails at the configural level due to convergence issues, preventing any meaningful invariance testing. Intrinsic Value achieves marginal configural invariance (CFI = 0.970) and metric invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.002$), but fails scalar invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.046$). The factor structure and loadings are consistent across groups, but intercepts differ. Personal Utility Value fails at the configural level (CFI = 0.779, RMSEA = 0.226), with negative variances indicating model misspecification. Finally, Social Utility Value achieves marginal configural invariance (CFI = 0.933), but fails metric ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.012$) and scalar invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.020$). The factor structure is mostly consistent, but factor loadings and intercepts differ across groups. Negative variances and inconsistent loadings (e.g., AI on SUV) indicate model issues.

Overall, Intrinsic Value is the only factor to achieve total metric invariance, but it fails scalar invariance, preventing *t*-test comparisons. Self-Perception, Task Demand, and Social Utility Value achieve marginal configural invariance but fail metric invariance, indicating differences in factor loadings. Socialization Influences, Personal Utility Value, and Task Return fail at the configural level, with Task Return not converging. CN consistently contributes more to misfit at the configural level, suggesting cultural differences in how these constructs are perceived.

5.3. Comparative study

To compare the motivational factors of the (D)FIT-Choice scale between Swiss and Chinese student teachers, independent sample *t*-tests were conducted for factors meeting minimum reliability and configural invariance criteria. Based on the reliability analysis (Table 2), most factors demonstrated acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$), except for Fallback Career (CH $\alpha = 0.689$, CN $\alpha = 0.681$), Intrinsic Value Teaching (CH $\alpha = 0.649$), Intrinsic Value Subject (CH $\alpha = 0.668$), Job Transferability (CN $\alpha = 0.667$), and Social Dissuasion (CH $\alpha = 0.604$). Configural invariance testing (Table 3) confirmed that higher-order factors Self-Perception (PTA, PDTC; CFI = 0.982), Task Demand (EC, HD; CFI = 0.969), Intrinsic Value (IVT, IVS; CFI = 0.970), and Social Utility Value (SFCA, ESE, MSC, WCA, CDT, AI; CFI = 0.933) achieved marginal to good configural fit, while Socialization Influences (PTLE, PDTU, SI, SD; CFI = 0.884), Personal Utility Value (JS, TFF, JT; CFI = 0.779), and Task Return (SS, SY) were excluded due to poor fit or convergence issues. Further invariance testing revealed that Intrinsic Value achieved metric invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.002$) but failed scalar invariance ($\Delta\text{CFI} = -0.046$), providing stronger support for the comparability of IVT and IVS observed mean scores across groups, though potential intercept differences may introduce some bias. In contrast, Self-Perception, Task Demand, and Social Utility Value failed metric invariance (ΔCFI ranging from -0.012 to -0.029), suggesting that the observed mean scores of their first-order factors (PTA, PDTC; EC, HD; SFCA, ESE, MSC, WCA, CDT, AI) may not fully represent the same constructs in CH and CN, making these comparisons more exploratory. Fallback Career (FC) and Satisfaction (SN) were included as standalone factors. Consequently, *t*-tests were conducted for PTA, PDTC, EC, HD, IVT, IVS, SFCA, ESE, MSC, WCA, CDT, AI, and SN, with results interpreted cautiously due to low reliability in some factors and the lack of metric invariance for most factors, except IVT and IVS.

To compare the two samples, first the assumption of equal variances was tested. For this, the Levene's test for homogeneity of variance was conducted for each variable. Based on whether the assumption of equal variances was violated or not, Welch's *t* or Student's *t* was used respectively. The *t*-test revealed significant differences between the two groups in 19 of the 23 factors influencing their decision to become a teacher (see Table 4 and Fig. 1).

In the case of Self-perceptions, Chinese student teachers score

significantly higher in their Perceived Digital Teaching Competence with a large effect size (PDTC: $M_{\text{CH}} = 4.19$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.434$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 5.26$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.208$; $t(414) = -8.309$, $p < 0.001$, $d = -0.820$), while there are no significant differences in their general Perceived Teaching Abilities (PTA: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.92$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.763$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 5.79$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.220$; $t(395) = 1.324$, $p = 0.186$, $d = 0.127$). Regarding Intrinsic Value, Swiss student teachers score significantly higher with large effect sizes in both, Intrinsic Value Teaching (IVT: $M_{\text{CH}} = 6.48$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.556$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 5.77$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 0.906$; $t(393) = 9.832$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.944$) and Intrinsic Value Subject (IVS: $M_{\text{CH}} = 6.11$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.763$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 5.20$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.324$; $t(383) = 8.739$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.937$). In Task Demand, it is also Swiss student teachers who score significantly higher with medium effect sizes in Expert Career (EC: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.75$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.878$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 5.16$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.236$; $t(410) = 5.689$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.550$) and a large effect size in High Demand (HD: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.88$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.811$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 4.91$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.123$; $t(411) = 10.240$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.992$).

Regarding Social Utility Value, Swiss students score significantly higher with large effect sizes in Enhance Social Equity (ESE: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.55$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.248$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 4.08$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.150$; $t(414) = 12.495$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.234$), Make a Social Contribution (MSC: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.78$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.127$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 3.94$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.360$; $t(413) = 15.134$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.478$), Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents (SFCA: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.94$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.952$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 3.93$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.314$; $t(411) = 18.031$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.747$), and Work with Children and Adolescents (WCA: $M_{\text{CH}} = 5.62$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.182$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 4.28$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.012$; $t(414) = 12.445$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.229$). Regarding the factor Contribute to the Digital Transformation (CDT: $M_{\text{CH}} = 4.06$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.419$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 4.19$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.073$; $t(330) = -0.979$, $p = 0.328$, $d = -0.098$) there are no significant differences between Swiss and Chinese student teachers. However, when it comes to considering Artificial Intelligence Chinese students score significantly higher with a small effect size (AI: $M_{\text{CH}} = 4.03$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 1.608$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 4.47$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.523$; $t(414) = -2.830$, $p = 0.005$, $d = -0.279$).

Finally, Satisfaction with the career choice is significantly higher for Swiss student teachers with a large effect size (SN: $M_{\text{CH}} = 6.18$, $SD_{\text{CH}} = 0.902$; $M_{\text{CN}} = 3.94$, $SD_{\text{CN}} = 1.511$; $t(388) = 18.717$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.795$).

6. Discussion

6.1. Scale validation

The first research question, "Is the (D)FIT-Choice scale a valid and reliable instrument across different cultural contexts?" was assessed through reliability analysis and measurement invariance testing using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) across Swiss and Chinese student teachers.

The reliability analysis indicated that most higher-order factors exhibited good to excellent internal consistency, except for Salary, Fallback Career, and Job Transferability, which showed lower reliability. The reduced reliability of these factors may stem from cultural differences in interpretation. For instance, salary expectations and market conditions likely differ between Switzerland and China, as well as across the three regions analyzed in this study, leading to high variability in responses. Similarly, perceptions of teaching as a fallback career or the transferability of teaching qualifications may vary due to diverse experiences and labor market contexts, contributing to inconsistent responses. Measurement invariance was assessed to determine whether the factor structures hold across groups. Configural invariance testing revealed that Self-Perception demonstrated the strongest fit, followed by Task Demand and Intrinsic Value, which showed acceptable fit based on standard indices, though potential misfit was noted, particularly in the Chinese sample. Social Utility Value exhibited marginal fit with signs of instability, while Socialization Influences and Personal Utility Value demonstrated poor fit, and Task Return could not be evaluated due to convergence issues, suggesting that their factor

Table 4
Independent Samples T-Test, Swiss student teachers (CH) and Chinese student teachers (CN).

Factor	Statistic	df	p	Cohen's d	Switzerland (CH)		China (CN)	
					Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Artificial Intelligence	-2.830	414	0.005	-0.279	4.03	1.608	4.47	1.523
Contribute to the Digital Transformation ¹	-0.979	330	0.328	-0.098	4.06	1.419	4.19	1.073
Expert Career ¹	5.689	410	< 0.001	0.550	5.75	0.878	5.16	1.236
Enhance Social Equity	12.495	414	< 0.001	1.234	5.55	1.248	4.08	1.150
High Demand ¹	10.240	411	< 0.001	0.992	5.88	0.811	4.91	1.123
Intrinsic Value Subject ¹	8.739	383	< 0.001	0.937	6.11	0.763	5.20	1.324
Intrinsic Value Teaching ¹	9.832	393	< 0.001	0.944	6.48	0.556	5.77	0.906
Make a Social Contribution ¹	15.134	413	< 0.001	1.478	5.78	1.127	3.94	1.360
Perceived Digital Teaching Competence	-8.309	414	< 0.001	-0.820	4.19	1.434	5.26	1.208
Perceived Teaching Ability ¹	1.324	395	0.186	0.127	5.92	0.763	5.79	1.220
Shape the Future of Children and Adolescents ¹	18.031	411	< 0.001	1.747	5.94	0.952	3.93	1.314
Satisfaction ¹	18.717	388	< 0.001	1.795	6.18	0.902	3.94	1.511
Work with Children and Adolescents	12.445	414	< 0.001	1.229	5.62	1.182	4.28	1.012

¹ Welch's t-test applied because the assumption of equal variances was violated through Levene's test.

Fig. 2. Means comparison, Swiss student teachers (CH) and Chinese student teachers (CN).

structures are not equivalent across the analyzed countries. Further invariance testing showed that only Intrinsic Value achieved metric invariance, indicating equivalent factor loadings across groups, but it failed scalar invariance, suggesting differences in item intercepts. This contrasts with previous studies involving Switzerland and China, where factors such as Personal Utility Value and Task Return showed good fit [17], highlighting potential cultural or contextual differences in the current sample that may affect the measurement of these motivational factors.

The poor fit of Personal Utility Value and Task Return aligns with their low reliability, highlighting cultural differences in the perception of practical benefits (e.g., salary, job security) that may require item refinement for cross-cultural applicability. Both aspects are related to practical benefits of the teaching job, and it may be the case that practical benefits are perceived differently in different contexts. Given the differences in individual and collective values in Switzerland and China, respectively, individual practical benefits may be perceived significantly differently and therefore require different items to measure these contexts. China's strong cultural emphasis on practicality and economic stability [40,41], where securing a well-paying, stable job is highly valued, in line with Confucian values which emphasize responsibility

and family obligations [42], may be considered. Although Chinese student teachers perceive the teaching profession as a career with high demands but low rewards [21], Chinese student teachers in our sample perceive that the teaching profession requires less expert knowledge (EC) and less demand (HD) than their Swiss counterpart. This difference may be attributed to several factors unique to the Chinese context. In China, even students who do not major in education but attend prestigious universities still have opportunities to obtain decent teaching jobs in big cities (e.g., [43]). Moreover, obtaining a teaching certificate in mainland China is relatively straightforward. Both education and non-education students can earn the certificate by passing an exam and an interview, without the need for prior teaching experience, further training or internships (National Education Examinations Authority., n. d.). This makes it easier for Chinese student teachers to gain the qualifications to become formal teachers, which could explain their lower perceived task demands compared with Swiss student teachers. Additionally, the task return for Chinese student teachers is relatively high, especially in cities like Shenzhen and Hong Kong, where teachers earn salaries that are typically three to four times the local average income ([44]; Hong Kong Federation of Education [45]). Teachers in these regions also enjoy job stability, as public school positions are classified as

public institution roles, meaning they are government-funded, come with official establishment status, and are difficult to lose. This stability, along with a decent salary, contributes to the perception of higher task return among Chinese student teachers. Finally, the teaching standards and job opportunities in China vary significantly across different regions. While it may be challenging to secure a teaching job in highly competitive cities like Shenzhen and Hong Kong, there are still opportunities in less developed areas. This regional disparity further reinforces the perception of lower task demands and higher task returns for Chinese student teachers.

6.2. Differences between countries

The second research question, “Are there significant differences between Chinese and Swiss student teachers based on the (D) FIT-Choice scale?” was assessed by means of an independent sample *t*-test. A general overview of cultural factors that may affect different motivations is presented, and a special focus is put on the digital-related motives.

6.2.1. Cultural differences

Our study found that Swiss student teachers were more motivated by Social Utility Values than their Chinese counterparts, concretely, they wanted to enhance social equity (ESE), make a social contribution (MSC), shape the future of children and adolescents (SFCA), and work with children and adolescents (WCA). Furthermore, Swiss student teachers also expressed having a higher intrinsic motivation for teaching in general (IVT) and for teaching their own subject (IVS). These factors indicate that Swiss student teachers may be more focused on personal fulfilment and social contributions as key motivators for their career choice, which may be associated to their higher Satisfaction (SN) with the career choice when comparing it to Chinese student teachers. Furthermore, Chinese students' dissatisfaction has been associated to factors such as high stress, low salaries, limited holidays, declining social status, students' misbehaviour, parents' poor attitudes, an unfair evaluation system, and unfulfilled educational reforms [22]. The focus of Swiss students on personal fulfilment can be explained based on a more individualistic society that prioritises intrinsic motivations such as personal growth, curiosity, and fulfilment [23,46], which at the same time may lead to a higher attainment value, meaning that student teachers feel they have better aligned their personal identity and their professional goals, therefore feeling more satisfied with this decision. Finally, the willingness of Swiss students to make a social contribution, may appear contradictory at first glance given the individualistic values of the Swiss society, however, this may indicate a personal commitment towards social improvement aligned with previous findings indicating higher civic engagement and volunteering in countries with strong direct democracy, as is the case in Switzerland [47].

6.2.2. Digital-related differences

One of the specific foci of this research was to see whether there are significant differences in student teachers' motivation to digitalise education in both countries. The results of this study indicate that Chinese student teachers are more influenced by a higher perceived digital teaching competence (PDTC) than their Swiss counterpart, although there are no differences when it comes to general Perceived Teaching Abilities (PTA). These student teachers have been exposed to technology extensively throughout their education, as exemplified by the Ten-Year Development Plan for Education Informatization implemented in 2011 [48] in comparison to the Swiss new curriculum Lehrplan21, which includes Media and Computer science education but started to be implemented in 2017 ([49,61]). Also, Chinese high-tech products, such as mobile payment systems (e.g., Alipay), are ubiquitous in mainland China. This exposure may contribute to their higher acceptance of technology, leading them to view themselves as more experienced and competent in integrating digital technologies into teaching and learning.

The adoption of technology in education can be further understood

through established theoretical frameworks such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [50], which posits that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are key determinants of an individual's intention to use technology. Chinese student teachers' higher PDTC aligns with TAM, suggesting that their extensive exposure to technology enhances their perception of its utility and ease of integration in educational settings. Additionally, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) [51,52] highlights the role of social influence and facilitating conditions, such as government initiatives in China, in shaping technology adoption. The Chinese government's policies, including the Ten-Year Development Plan for Education Informatization and subsequent AI-focused educational reforms ([29,48,62]), provide robust facilitating conditions that likely bolster Chinese student teachers' confidence and motivation to adopt digital tools.

Furthermore, when it comes to AI in education, Chinese student teachers also demonstrate greater enthusiasm for incorporating AI into the educational field. They show a strong commitment to preparing students to work with AI, leveraging its opportunities, and addressing its challenges. This could be due to Chinese Government initiatives and advancements in high technology use and the implementation of AI in education. For instance, the Chinese government has released official documents promoting digital education and AI-integrated teaching and learning ([29,62]). In response, many AI- and technology-related departments have been established within public university faculties of education in China (e.g., Shanghai Institute of AI Education, Faculty of Artificial Intelligence in Education of Central China Normal University), signalling that digital education and AI-related courses are now commonly integrated into student teachers' training. These initiatives resonate with findings from studies on technology adoption in education, which emphasize the importance of institutional support and training in fostering positive attitudes toward technology integration [53,54]. The establishment of specialized AI education departments in China reflects a proactive approach to building technological infrastructure and teacher capacity, further reinforcing technology adoption as described in the Diffusion of Innovations theory [55], where early adopters are supported by structural and cultural enablers.

So far, these findings suggest that Chinese student teachers are not only more open to integrating technology, particularly AI, into education but also perceive themselves as more capable in this domain, probably pushed by government initiatives. These differences in motivations, prior experience and perceived ability may influence the future introduction of technology and AI in education by future teachers, therefore shaping the future of education. In these lines, teacher education programmes should consider these differences when preparing future teachers for a digitally driven future. Research by Mishra & Koehler [56] on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework underscores the need for teacher education to integrate technological knowledge with pedagogical and content knowledge to effectively prepare teachers for technology-rich classrooms. The proactive integration of AI and digital education in Chinese teacher training programs exemplifies this approach, potentially giving Chinese student teachers an advantage in TPACK development compared to their Swiss counterparts.

While previous studies have indicated that individualistic countries with more power distance foster competitiveness and innovation [57], the results of this study show a different perspective. This discrepancy can be attributed to the nature of the education sector in Switzerland, which does not operate primarily based on values such as competitiveness and innovation. Instead, education systems are typically publicly funded and driven by alternative incentives such as equity, social development and long-term societal impact [58]. However, as studies in support of market-based reforms suggest, the introduction of competitive mechanisms such as school autonomy and performance-based accountability could potentially change this scenario [59,60], allowing individualistic countries to make use of their potential for innovation in education.

6.3. Limitations and future research

Although this study provides valuable insights into the motivations of student teachers in Switzerland and China, some limitations should be considered.

First, the study relied exclusively on self-report surveys, which may be subject to biases such as social desirability or response bias. Future studies should integrate observational methods or objective measures, such as classroom performance assessments or digital competency tests. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how motivations translate into teaching practices and professional development.

Second, the sampling strategy focussed on student teachers from specific cities in Switzerland (e.g. Zurich) and China (e.g. Shenzhen and Hong Kong). Therefore, the results may not be generalisable to other regions within these countries, especially those with different socio-economic contexts, education systems or levels of technological integration. Future studies should include more diverse and representative samples to ensure broader applicability. Also, cultural differences between Switzerland and China are considerable, and although Hofstede's dimensions and related frameworks offer a useful perspective, they have been criticised for oversimplifying cultural variations and not considering individual or regional differences within countries. This limitation could affect the interpretation of results related to cultural influences on motivation. Future studies should use more nuanced cross-cultural research approaches, including mixed-method designs, to account for these variations and deepen the analysis of how culture shapes teacher motivation.

Third, the adaptation and translation of the (D) FIT-Choice scale into an English version for use with Chinese student teachers may have introduced linguistic or cultural biases. Although efforts were made to ensure its cultural relevance through translation revisions, some items may have been interpreted differently in the two contexts. Concretely, Task Return, Personal Utility Value and Socialization Influences did not achieve good model fit across the two cultural contexts. Refinement of these factors such as revising items is necessary to ensure that they accurately measure teacher motivation in diverse cultural settings.

Fourth, measurement invariance testing revealed that the factor structures of most motivational factors were not fully equivalent across Swiss and Chinese student teachers. While Intrinsic Value showed equivalence in factor loadings, it exhibited differences in item intercepts, and Self-Perception, Task Demand, and Social Utility Value lacked equivalence in factor loadings, with Task Return, Personal Utility Value, and Socialization Influences failing to establish even basic structural equivalence. This lack of measurement invariance suggests that the constructs may not be directly comparable across the two groups, potentially affecting the validity of cross-cultural comparisons, including the *t*-tests conducted on observed mean scores. Additionally, cross-cultural response styles (e.g., preference for extreme or midpoint categories, acquiescence) may have affected how participants used the 7-point rating scales, contributing to the observed non-invariance and biasing between-group mean comparisons. Future research should focus on refining the (D) FIT-Choice scale to achieve measurement invariance, possibly by revising or removing problematic items, and explore partial invariance approaches to better understand which aspects of the constructs are comparable across cultures.

Furthermore, future research could use Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to compare the differences in the relationships between these factors in Switzerland and China. By addressing these limitations and exploring these future research directions, we could develop a deeper understanding of how cultural, economic, and technological factors shape teacher motivation in an increasingly digitised world, contributing to the design of more effective teacher training programs to foster the digitalisation of education.

7. Conclusions

Overall, this study partially validates the (D) FIT-Choice scale, demonstrating its applicability in different cultural contexts for some factors through its application with student teachers in Switzerland and China, though significant measurement challenges remain. Most higher-order factors showed good to excellent reliability, except for Salary, Fallback Career, Job Transferability, Task Return, Personal Utility Value, and Socialization Influences, which require further refinement to improve their cross-cultural applicability; however, model fit was only marginal for most factors, with Self-Perception showing the strongest fit, followed by Task Demand, Intrinsic Value, and Social Utility Value, while Task Return, Personal Utility Value, and Socialization Influences exhibited poor fit or convergence issues. The results reveal some differences in student teachers' motives to become a teacher, with Swiss student teachers being more influenced by intrinsic motivations than their Chinese counterparts, a finding supported by the metric invariance of Intrinsic Value, though their greater willingness to contribute to society is more exploratory due to the lack of metric invariance for Social Utility Value. Conversely, Chinese student teachers showed higher perceived digital competence for teaching and a greater willingness to integrate AI into their future teaching career, likely driven by broad national initiatives and technological advances in China, though these findings are preliminary due to measurement non-equivalence in the respective factors. These differences suggest that socio-cultural, economic, and technological factors, alongside measurement challenges, play a significant role in shaping teachers' motivation and digital readiness, underlining the importance of tailoring teacher education programs to their specific contexts.

Beyond its empirical findings, this study offers several strengths that advance research on teacher motivation in education systems undergoing digital transformation. First, it provides one of the first cross-cultural analyses of motives related to digital technology and artificial intelligence for becoming a teacher, using data from two contrasting educational contexts. Second, by expanding and empirically testing the (D) FIT-Choice scale with AI-related components, the study offers partial cross-cultural validation of the instrument and identifies specific dimensions that require refinement, thereby updating an established framework for contemporary demands. Thirdly, the integration of measurement invariance analyses reinforces the methodological rigour of the study and supports a more cautious but interpretable comparison between cultural environments. Taken together, these contributions underscore the value of the study for understanding how emerging technologies shape professional motivations in teacher education and for informing the further development of motivational frameworks tailored to digital and AI-driven educational contexts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Judit Martínez-Moreno: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Xinyan Zhou:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Dominik Petko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Thomas K.F. Chiu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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